

INVESTIGATION OF SOME METHODS OF DETERMINING THE GLYCERIDE COMPOSITION OF FATS. PART I.

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A synthetic fat from fully saturated, di-saturated mono-unsaturated, mono-saturated di-unsaturated glycerides has been prepared and the component glycerides have been estimated.

The work of Hilditch and several others have shown the importance of determining the glyceride composition of fats, as the physical properties of fats are modified considerably by the composition of the component glycerides (cf. Hilditch, "Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", Oxford University Press, 1939, p. 181).

The method of estimating tri-saturated glycerides has been standardised, but some of the other methods require direct confirmation by analysis of mixtures of glycerides of known composition. Several saturated and unsaturated glycerides of known structure have been synthesised by the present authors and the applicability of the various methods of determining the glyceride composition, so far used, is being investigated.

Kartha and Menon (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1943, 17A, 114) claim to have developed a tentative method of determining the composition of fats containing di-saturated, mono-unsaturated glycerides (GS_2U) and di-unsaturated mono-saturated glycerides (GSU_2).

In a fat containing tri-saturated glycerides (GS_3), di-saturated mono-unsaturated (GS_2U), di-unsaturated mono-saturated (GSU_2) and tri-unsaturated glycerides (GU_3), oxidation will give a mixture of GS_3 and mono-azelaol di-saturated (GS_2A), diazelaol mono-saturated (GSA_2) and tri-azelaol glycerides (GA_3). Of these, the first (GS_3) is neutral and can be separated from the acidic products. This forms the basis of the method developed by Hilditch and Lea (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3106) for estimating fully saturated glycerides in a fat. It has been found by Hilditch (*loc. cit.*, p. 406) that from a mixture of mono-azelaol di-saturated (GS_2A), di-azelaol mono-saturated (GSA_2) glycerides potassium bicarbonate extracts only the mono-azelaol di-saturated glycerides completely, and partly the di-azelaol mono-saturated glycerides. On the basis of this observation Kartha and Menon (*loc. cit.*) suggest that potassium bicarbonate extracts would give mainly mono-azelaol di-saturated glycerides containing a little of di-azelaol mono-saturated glycerides and from the saponification value of the mixture it is possible to calculate the quantity of GS_2U , and hence the composition of the fat as regards the GS_2U and GS_3 can be calculated with accuracy. For the calculation of GSU_2 Kartha and Menon suggest that in the mixture of fats, considered above, if GS_3 and GS_2U are known and the saturated acid content, if be known, the

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quantity of saturated acids present as GSU_2 can be calculated from the difference between the total saturated fatty acids and the saturated fatty acid present in GS_3 and GS_2U . This, however, involves the assumption that the saturated fatty acids are evenly distributed in the three types of glycerides. The method of Kartha and Menon appears to be straight forward and has the advantage that it requires small quantities of fats. The method has not been tested, however, so far for its accuracy on synthetic fats of known glyceride composition. We have prepared a synthetic fat from fully saturated glyceride (GS_3), di-saturated mono-unsaturated (GS_2U), mono-saturated di-unsaturated (GSU_2) and tri-unsaturated (GU_3) and we have estimated the component glycerides using Kartha and Menon's method. The results are described below.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tristearin was prepared by using the method of Clarkson and Malkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 666).

Triolein.—Oleic acid (Merck) was converted into its methyl ester and fractionally distilled. The main fraction was hydrolysed and the oleic acid distilled. The acid did not show the presence of linolic or linolenic acids. This oleic acid was converted into triolein in the usual manner. The product obtained was water-white and had iodine value (Wijs), 86.5 (I. V. calc., 86.2).

Mono-stearo di-olein was prepared from pure oleic acid and mono-stearin according to the method described by Daubert, Spiegl and Longenecker (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2144). The product had I.V. (Wijs), 56.82 (calc., 57.2).

Mono-oleo di-stearin was prepared by the method described by Daubert, *et al.*, (*loc. cit.*). The final product had I.V., 26.18 (calc., 28.4).

Table I gives the properties and composition of the fat prepared by mixing the above mentioned glycerides.

TABLE I

Composition of the fat.			Properties of the fat.	
			Obs.	Calc.
Tristearin	25.75%	Iodine value 42.75 42.6
Triolein	24.60	Sapon. value 188.1 189.6
1-Mono-stearo-2:3-diolein		25.37	Titre test 41°
1-Mono-oleo-2:3-distearin		24.25	Acid value	... Negligible

The fat was oxidised by potassium permanganate following strictly the method adopted by Kartha and Menon (*loc. cit.*). The following table gives the relevant data for the calculations of the component glycerides.

TABLE II

Total fat taken	5.934 g.
Wt. of tristearin obtained (I)	1.419
Wt. of mono-azelaio and di-azelaio glycerides (II)	1.39
Saponification of (II)	295.6
Wt. of mono-azelaio glycerides from S.V.	1.242
Wt. of mono-azelaio from equivalent	1.25

The weight of mono-azelaio glycerides could be checked by taking equivalent weight of the mixture (I), as the saturated acid in the glyceride is known to be stearic acid.

Hence, the composition of fat is as follows :—

	Found.	Taken.
Tri-saturated glyceride	23.84%	25.75%
Mono-unsaturated di-saturated glyceride	23.42	24.25

It will be seen from the above table that the composition of the fat, found by the above procedure, agrees within 5% of the theoretical as regards the trisaturated glycerides (GS_3) and di-saturated mono-unsaturated glycerides (GS_2U).

As in our synthetic fat, stearic acid is the only saturated acid we could have calculated the mono-saturated di-unsaturated glyceride (GSU_2), but we have not done so as it would mean only an additional arithmetical computation.

We believe therefore that this method is suitable for estimating tri-saturated (GS_3) and di-saturated mono-unsaturated (GS_2U) glycerides only. The estimation of the quantity of mono-saturated di-unsaturated (GSU_2) will be uncertain and will not be accurate as the errors in estimating GS_3 and GS_2U will be multiplied in the estimation of GSU_2 .

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